

Bio-geophysical variables measured at ICOS

Summary for CalVal evaluation

The table below provides a summary of the main bio-geophysical variables measured at the ICOS Class1 and Class2 stations that can be of interest for CalVal activities. For each variable (or group of variables) a short summary of the protocol used is reported.

Note that CP in the table states for “Continuous Plot”, a permanent sampling area that are defined after a more extensive sampling using 20 smaller sampling areas (SP) selected with a stratified random design. The CP are positioned in areas that represent the species, biomass and LAI distribution in the Target Area.

The Target Area is the portion of ecosystem (defined geographically) that we want to monitor with the eddy covariance system.

In forest, the CP are 2000m² (circular, 25.24m of radius) and the SP are circular, 700m², visited only once every 5-10 years

In cropland the CP have sizes function of the crop type cut measurements are done also in the SP more regularly

In grassland there are no CP and measurements are done directly and periodically in the SP, using also a set of sub-areas around each of the 20 SPs.

Variable	Protocol applied
Land Surface Albedo	<p>Measured with a 4-components radiometer (SW and LW) installed between 2 and 10 meters above the canopy on the eddy covariance tower.</p> <p>The sensor must be heated and ventilated, corrected for the sensor temperature and calibrated every 2-3 years.</p> <p>In general, the Kipp&Zonen CNR4 is used.</p> <p>Implemented in all the ICOS sites active, data collected every 20 seconds.</p>
Phenology	<p>It is under implementation using the StartDot camera and the same routine applied in the Phenocam network in all the Class1 stations.</p> <p>Under evaluation the possibility to install also below canopy cameras in forest for the understory phenology</p> <p>Data collected every halfhour.</p> <p>See also the FAPAR</p>
SIF	<p>Currently not measured (a couple of tests with the FLOX sensor).</p> <p>However the sites are measuring carbon exchange and ecosystem photosynthesis can be estimated (GPP), that scales with SIF.</p>

<p>Land Surface Temperature</p>	<p>Currently under discussion for the implementation.</p> <p>At the moment only outgoing LW radiation is monitored but ICOS is evaluating Infrared thermometers and also Thermal Cameras.</p> <p>In both cases they would be mounted on the eddy covariance tower.</p> <p>It is possible to suggest the best strategy and to support the measurement in the ICOS General Assembly</p> <p>Type of sensor, protocol, calibration plan to be defined</p>
<p>FAPAR</p>	<p>All the sites have PPFDF sensors IN and OUT on top of the towers. Class1 stations have also diffuse PPFDF.</p> <p>In a number of forest sites it is under implementation a network of below canopy incident PPFDF.</p> <p>A minimum of 5 sensors are installed at DBH in each CP.</p> <p>Between 2 and 5 CP are present in each of the stations (minimum 2 in the Class2 stations, minimum 4 in the Class 1)</p> <p>The sensors must be cross-calibrated with the incoming PAR sensor every year.</p> <p>If needed it can be discussed the installation of ground reflected PAR sensors.</p> <p>Data are collected at 20 seconds time resolution</p>
<p>LAI</p>	<p>LAI is measured in campaigns with methods that are ecosystem specific.</p> <p>In forest DHP are used except if LAI is larger than 6 (the ceptometers are used). DHP are collected 6 times per year, between 9 and 13 pictures per CP. Cameras are fully characterized. The variable measured in PAI. Understory LAI is measured once per year with destructive sampling in one sub-area per CP.</p> <p>In grasslands destructive sampling and bulk height are used in about 60 points in the Target Area. Measurements are done 6 times per year. In case it is possible also the ceptometer is used.</p> <p>In croplands the ceptometer is used, with measurements 6 times per year in specific crop growth stages in 20 points in the Target Area. Also parallel destructive sampling is used for comparison.</p> <p>Currently the development of a protocol for the estimation of PAI in forest using above and below canopy PAR is under finalization.</p> <p>Spatial variability can be very important.</p>

<p>Volumetric Soil Water Content</p>	<p>Between 2 and 5 vertical profiles of temperature and soil water content sensors are installed (generally in the CPs), with at least 5 depths and up to 1m depth.</p> <p>Data are measured every 60 seconds.</p> <p>Sensors must be either Time Domain Reflectometry, Frequency Domain Reflectometry, Amplitude Domain Reflectometry, or based on the capacitance method</p> <p>Same sensor model must be used in all the profile at the same site</p>
<p>Leaves nutrients</p>	<p>If of interest, chemical elements content of leaves is measured between 1 and 3 times per year through 30 samples collected from the most representative species.</p> <p>Elements include Ca, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, C, N, P, K and Zn, in addition to the LMA ration</p>